

Navabrahma Temple at Alampur

Dr. Ekula Venkata Padmaja

Assoc. Prof. Dept. of History & Archaeology, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur.

Corresponding Author- Dr. Ekula Venkata Padmaja

Email- padmajaekula@gmail.com

Abstract: Alampur is situated in Mahabubnagar in (Andhra Pradesh) present in Telangana, it is famous for Saivite Kshetra and Devi Jogulamba as listed in Astadasa Sakti Pitas. This Alampur is famous for Navabrahma temples and is located on the left bank of river Tungabhadra, the temple at kudali Sangameswara was transplanted and erected at Alampur. The inscriptions and architecture belong to Chalukyas of Badami Kalyani, the Architecture of Alampur temple follows the Nagara tradition and Dravida tradition.

Keywords: Chalukyas of Badami Kalyani, Dravida, Nagara tradition.

Alampur is a taluk head quarter in the district Mahabubnagar in Telangana. It can be approached from Hyderabad or Kurnool. The town is 9 kms from the Alampur Railway station. This town had hoary antiquity. It is a Saivite kshetra and formed as a Western gateway to Srisailem, Devi Jogulamba is also listed in Astadasa Sakti Pitha. This temple is directly located on the left bank of river Tungabhadra. This complex is enclosed by a prakara wall with two entrances. This Alampur temple complex was provided with a massive stone protective wall on its eastern side, on the river bank. River Tungabhadra flows as an Uttaravair and merges into the river Krishna at Kudali Sangameswaram. At Srisailem, river Krishna a hydro-electric project was constructed. Due to this project number of villages in Mahabubnagar and Kurnool were submerged under water or reservoir. The temple at Kudali Sangameswaram was transplanted and erected at Alampur by the Archaeological survey of India. Because of this project Nava Brahma temple complex was also in danger, for this reason this protective wall was constructed between Tungabhadra and temple complex. This temple complex was declared as a monument Archaeological survey of India. They constructed a museum and placed the loose sculptures and inscriptions which were collected from this complex.

From the inscriptions we know that Alampur was known in the historical times as Alampura, Hatampura, Alampuri and Alampur. Alampuri is mentioned in an inscription of the time of Krishnadevaraya of Vijayanagara. Alampur is situated on the western bank of the Tungabhadra River and the main temple is located between the Vedavati and Nadavati rivers. Alampur is referred to as Daksina Varanasi Kasi Ksetra and the western gateway of Srisailem.

The earliest inscriptions at Alampur to the period of Chalukyas of Badami, the three inscriptions found. One is of the time of Vinayaditya and other two of the reigns of

Vijayaditya. The inscription at the time of Vinayaditya in the Svarga Brahma temple states that the temple is honour of the queen (Mahadevi) of Vinayaditya was caused to be constructed by Lokaditya-Ela-Arasa. So, this inscription is more important to fix the time of the construction of the Svarga Brahma temple. The inscription of Vijayaditya dated 704 A.D. is on the slab fixed into the for-wall near the Devadroni and states that the enclosure in question was set up at the instance of the Chalukyan ruler and dedicated to the worshipful Isanacaryaswami. On the same slab there is another fragmentary inscription with similar contents. These inscriptions together with the architectural style form the basis for assigning the construction of the "Nava Brahma" temples are interesting as similar practice is met with at the other centers of art of the Chalukyas of Badami like pattadakal and satyavolu.

According to a local story Sri Brahmeswara Kshetra Mahatyam, these Navva Brahma temples were built by a Rasa Siddha with the blessings of gods. A king named Vilasat Raja who was a nastika attempted to ruin the temples and cursed by the siddha lost all his army and wealth. One day the king wandering in the forest met a deer through a hunter and the deer told the king that he should go to Brahmeswara Kshetra and do penance there for some time and reconstruct the temples to get over his sins, the king in the sculpture is identified with Vilasat Raja.

An episode of deer and hunter is carved on the pillar at the narrow entrance to the fortress. On one side of the pillar, the scene of a deer feeding its little one as a hunter is waiting in the vicinity and another scene of a hunter aiming to shoot an arrow at the deer are carved. On another side of the pillar the scene of a hunter standing in Anjali pose before a king and his queen and the attendant standing in Anjali pose before the deer are carved. There are on the ceiling of the Mahadvara or the main entrance sculptures of Vishnu, Siva as Andhakasura Samharamurti and Brahma. In a small shrine beside

the entrance there is an image of a goddess locally called Kamakshi. She is found handed seated deity, holding damaru, khadga, trisula and patra in her hand. This shrine was built in the year 1353 A.D. who was pradhani of Mahamandalesvara Hemmadideva.

Description of the Temples:

In this complex nine Nava Brahma temple complex contains 9 temples which are dedicated to Siva. Among these, Bala Brahma temple is main shrine and located in the center of the compound. In these temples eight are in Nagara tradition and the Taraka Brahma temple is in Dravida tradition.

Taraka Brahma Temple:

This temple was built in sand stone and it is a unique model of Dravida Vimana exhibiting the sukanasa feature common to the nagara style. This temple faces east and consists of a square the garbhagriha an antharala. It is a ruined temple the garbhagriha is in a ruin state.

On basis of construction these temples are two phases, the phase belongs to Vikramaditya 652-681 A.D. and the latter to the ruling period of Vinayaditya, Vijayaditya, Vikramaditya and Kirthivarman 682-750 A.D. the temple Kumara Brahma, Arka Brahma, Bala Brahma belongs to first phase, other temples belong to second phase.

The Kumara Brahma Temple:

The pillars of the porch in this temple are noteworthy for the fineness of the carvings. The lintel of the hall door-frame is peculiar in that a row of seven heads are carved on it. In general plan, this temple is like the other Nava Brahma temples.

Swarga Brahma Temple:

This temple was constructed towards the end of the 7th century A.D. the entrance of the temple has a rectangular hall, which is divided into a nave and side aisles by the use of pillars connecting the passage. The panels on the outer walls carry the reliefs of Krishna leela, animals Garuda nose faces and Matrumurti. Although there had been relief carvings in Aihole and Pattadakal, the pantheism here shows a passionate enthusiasm for exaltation of human form to divine status. On the wall sculptures depicted the Lingodbhavamurti of Shiva, inset into a tall phallus, with worshipping figures in a rectangular panel from which Linga is carved. And a truncated figure shows the remains of a dynamic sculpture of Shiva as Tirpurasura Samharamurti. The mobility of the carving skillfully releases energies into the universe with terrifying violence. Another broken figure is a relief of Gangavatarana, again as a demonstration of the Alampur sculptor's genius for release of potential power of the gods. A similar sculpture of Shiva involved in the Tandava dance is a heroic image. The frenzy of the movement is caught in the ecstatic moment, by some

Viswakarma, realising himself through the expression of muscular energies into the universal image of dance incarnate. The Swarga Brahma temple has a six-pillar porch on the east. The purnaghata pillars being decorated with amalakas. There are horned dwarapalas by the doorway. Ganga and Yamuna are symbolically carved on the door-frame with the Garudanaga motif above. The temple has a curvilinear sikhara of the northern style, with a figure of dancing Shiva carved in the chaitya windows of the sukanasi.

Padma Brahma Temple:

This temple was like in the form of Swarga Brahma temple. Apart from the sculpture the two dwarapalikas near the square gateway, with the flying figure on the top, the sculptures on the façade of this temple have all been destroyed.

Garuda Brahma Temple:

Modelled on the Padma Brahma, this temple is distinguished by elaborate carvings on the pillars inside the hall, with the cool shadow secured for the extension of consciousness into the non-sensuous realms of clam.

Bala Brahma Temple: This temple remains in worship through the centuries therefore, it has often been renovated. The images are a mixture of routine sculptures like Jogulamba, Durga, Narasimha and the Rishis. In the courtyard are images of Mukhalinga, Sahasralinga and Mahishassuramardini. The most vital image is the mother goddess in the small shrine.

Arka Brahma Temple:

This temple roof was disappeared and it was in ruin state.

Vishva Brahma Temple:

The plan of the Vishva Brahma temple resembles the Swarga Brahma, except that it has no porch. The sculptures of the outer side walls are also similar, both in theme and execution, though the virtuosity has disappeared of the vandal's axe. Thus, the figure of Trivikramarka might have been a magnificent carving. When it was whole. Also, the Gangavatarana was once a highly energetic sculpture. The mithunas are also damaged. The floral reliefs of makaras and birds with flying figures indicate the lyricism of desire flowing through them from the springtime of Chalukyan sensibility.

The Vira Brahma Temple:

This temple in style is like the others of the group.

The Local Museum:

This museum contains the richest collection of Hindu sculptures. The sculptures and inscriptional slabs in the museum have been collected from places, in and around the Alampur. The sculptures are Daksha, A sage and his two

wives, Subramanya and Valli, A warrior couple,
Nataraj, Mahisasuramardini, Surya, etc.

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